

METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING TOPICS OF THE ELECTRICITY SECTION BASED ON CASE TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. *This article discusses the methodology for teaching the topic “Laws of Direct Current” in the “Electricity and Magnetism” section through case-study technology. The case-study method helps students develop independent thinking, problem-solving skills, and the ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practical situations. The article presents a practical lesson based on a real-life household electricity problem involving electrical overload. Students are divided into small groups and asked to identify the causes of power interruption, suggest possible solutions, and propose preventive measures. Through discussion, students learn that simultaneous use of high-power appliances can exceed the permitted electrical load and cause circuit breakers to trip. The lesson also emphasizes load management, correct power calculation, energy-efficient appliances, separate electrical lines, and smart monitoring systems. Overall, the case-study approach strengthens students’ understanding of direct current laws and prepares them for practical professional problem solving.*

Keywords: *case study, electric power, electricity meter, electricity and magnetism, problem, problem solutions, problem prevention, electrical overload, energy efficiency, independent thinking.*

Introduction

According to Resolution No. PQ-5032 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 19, 2021, “**On Measures to Improve the Quality of Education in the Field of Physics and Develop Scientific Research,**” the main goals and objectives include introducing integrative principles for teaching physics in higher education institutions, organizing the training of personnel in new specialties that are in high demand in the education market, and increasing the coverage of young people with physics education [1].

In order to implement these tasks, various scientific research activities are being carried out in the process of teaching physics. However, a number of problems related to training specialists who are competitive in the labor market, have thoroughly mastered the fundamentals of the subject, and possess professional skills and competencies have not yet been fully resolved.

The use of case technology in teaching general physics sections, particularly the “**Electricity and Magnetism**” section, can develop students’ independent learning and thinking skills. However, this method cannot be applied to all topics, because for each topic it is necessary to identify a problem that has several possible solutions, and students must have sufficient knowledge to solve that problem. Therefore, it is advisable to use the **case-study method** in practical classes after theoretical knowledge on a particular topic has been provided during lectures [2].

Materials and Methods

Below is a lesson plan for a practical lesson on the topic “**Laws of Direct Current**” in the subject “**Electricity and Magnetism,**” conducted on the basis of the case-study method. The practical lesson may be organized in the following four stages [4].

Stage 1: 10 minutes. Attendance is checked. Students are divided into three small groups. As a continuation of the topic “**Laws of Direct Current,**” the assignment based on the **case-study method** is explained to students using slides or handout materials.

Case Assignment

The Yuldoshev family, who live in Jizzakh city, moved into a new apartment in a multi-storey building. Their apartment has all modern household appliances: a refrigerator, an air conditioner, a washing machine, an electric kettle, a television, a microwave oven, a vacuum cleaner, and a computer. In their daily life, this family often used these appliances at the same time.

One evening, the following situation occurred: in the kitchen, the electric kettle and the microwave oven were turned on at the same time; the air conditioner was running; the washing machine was in washing mode; and at that moment, the vacuum cleaner was also switched on. Suddenly, the electricity in the apartment went out. The circuit breaker on the electricity meter had tripped. At first, they reset it manually, but this situation repeated several times. The family thought that the electrical appliances were faulty or that the cables had been connected incorrectly. However, when they called a technician, he said that the problem was not in the wiring.

Students are required to do the following:

- identify possible causes, that is, the reasons for interruptions in the electricity supply;
- provide solutions to the situation;
- determine measures to prevent such situations, that is, interruptions in the electricity supply.

Stage 2: 30 minutes

At this stage, students complete the tasks in the case assignment based on the knowledge they gained during lectures on the topic “**Laws of Direct Current.**”

The following tasks are assigned to each small group according to the case assignment:

Group 1: identify the causes of power outages in the electricity supply;

Group 2: find solutions to problems in the electricity supply;

Group 3: determine what measures should be taken to prevent such a situation from occurring.

Stage 3: 30 minutes

At this stage, one student from Group 1 explains the problem described above, namely what causes interruptions in the electricity supply in households. The causes presented are discussed among all groups.

The Main Cause of the Problem

In this situation, the main problem is the occurrence of electrical overload. The apartment’s electrical network is designed for a maximum power of 5 kW. However, because several high-power appliances were used at the same time, students discuss that the total power consumption exceeded the permitted limit.

Then, one student from Group 2 explains the possible solutions to this problem. The answers given are discussed with the students. It is emphasized that the problem is not simply a matter of “using fewer appliances.” Rather, it is a matter of load management, modernization of the network, and optimization of the protection system.

After that, one student from Group 3 explains the measures for preventing the problem. The ideas, suggestions, and recommendations presented are discussed collectively. Students are informed that, in order to prevent this problem, it is advisable to monitor the load, calculate power correctly, and avoid using high-power appliances at the same time. The following advantages of these measures are explained to them.

Limiting the appliances used at the same time. High-power appliances, such as the washing machine, air conditioner, electric kettle, microwave oven, and vacuum cleaner, should not be turned on at the same time. The load should be distributed over time. For example, the washing machine should be used at another time rather than in the evening. This is the simplest and most effective method.

Regularly calculating the total power. The power of each appliance, measured in watts or kilowatts, is indicated in its technical passport.

Formula:

The total power must not exceed the network limit, for example, 5 kW.

Increasing the electricity supply capacity. If many appliances are used regularly, it is necessary to increase the electricity supply capacity to 7–10 kW, check the cross-section of the input cable, and install a circuit breaker with a suitable rating. Before replacing the circuit breaker with a higher-rated one, the cable cross-section must be checked [3].

Organizing separate electrical lines. High-power appliances, such as an air conditioner, washing machine, and electric stove, should be connected through a separate circuit breaker and a separate cable. This distributes the load evenly and increases safety.

Using energy-efficient appliances. These include:

- inverter air conditioners;
- A or A+++ class appliances.

This reduces total consumption by 20–40%.

Installing a load monitoring system. This includes:

- a smart meter;
- a load-limiting device.

Results

When the limit is exceeded, this system temporarily turns off certain appliances and prevents the circuit breaker from tripping.

Stage 4: 10 minutes

At this stage, the teacher identifies the group that actively participated in the lesson, as well as the most knowledgeable and active student, and encourages them. Then, the teacher assesses the students who actively participated in all groups. Pre-prepared independent study assignments are distributed to the students. They are instructed to become familiar with these independent study assignments, and answers are provided to the questions they do not understand or are interested in regarding the assignment. Literature sources are provided to help them find relevant information for the independent study questions and tasks. Students are asked to express their opinions about the lesson, and the lesson is concluded [4].

Discussion

In conclusion, it can be stated that when the practical lesson on the topic “**Laws of Direct Current,**” which belongs to the “**Electricity and Magnetism**” section, is conducted on the basis of the **case-study method**, students’ independent thinking and problem-solving abilities develop, and their theoretical knowledge of the topic covered in lectures is strengthened. If the knowledge

being studied is independently understood, perceived, and learned through facing difficulties, then this knowledge is mastered fully and deeply. All of this is also connected with developing learning skills, using time effectively when planning work activities, being responsible toward the subject being studied, self-monitoring, and correcting mistakes.

Conclusion

Students' constant engagement in intellectual activity develops their need for mental work and teaches them to use time effectively. In this way, it is possible to ensure the integration of future specialists' academic and scientific work, develop their independent learning activities, involve students in scientific research, and, on this basis, train highly qualified specialists.

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